

Flocculation Studies of Ferric Vanadate Sol at Different Stages of Dialysis

KRISHNA RAINA & K. L. HANDOO

Department of Chemistry, University of Sagar, Saugar (M.P.)

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Flocculation studies of positively charged ferric vanadate sol at its different stages of purity have been made by observing the changes in extinction of light at $450\text{ m}\mu$ during the stepwise addition of electrolyte (K_2SO_4) to the sol for a fixed time of flocculation. The changes in extinction in all the cases when plotted against electrolyte concentration give S-shaped curves. The feature of the curves can be described in three parts (a) first, where the extinction changes are slight, (b) second, where the higher electrolyte amounts increase the attractive potential to cause rapid flocculation. During this process redistribution of ions between the double layer and the dispersed medium takes place so that the system is still left with little repulsive potential. Under these conditions, the particles rearrange their positions to better contacts and thus compact flocs are formed; (c) third, where, with still higher electrolyte amounts, a net work of irregular flocs is formed which gives lower extinction values.

Tezak and Co-workers¹⁻³ in a number of publications have made tyndallometric studies of the coagulation process of several sols. Schulz and Matijevic⁴, in their studies of the coagulation of silver halides in statu nascendi, noticed two turbidity maxima with increasing $\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4$ concentration. The negatively charged silver halide first coagulated by the Th^{4+} ions. A further addition of the electrolyte made it stable and positively charged, and finally the sol was coagulated by the NO_3^- ion.

Tezak, Biffi and Cernicki⁵⁻⁶ have followed the methods of the coagulation process of the mixed systems of the halides, cyanide and thiocyanate of Ag by univalent counter ions. By using a nephelometric method, Dohrsetzer⁷ studied the influence of the nature and concentration of electrolytes and nonelectrolytes and temperature on the re-peptizability of the positive ferric hydroxide sol. Watillon and Schoepen⁸ followed the kinetics of coagulation of nearly isodisperse sols of ferric hydroxide in the presence of several concentrations of indifferent electrolytes. From the spectra obtained during coagulation and during re-peptization, a calculation of the relative number of primary particles, which reappeared at a given stage of the re-peptization, was possible. The effects of various parameters on particle growth rates of colloidal thoria prepared from a nitrate medium were studied by Chun, Wordsworth and Olson⁹ using turbidity and other optical techniques. They stated that the particle growth apparently occurred due to aggregation of crystallites and the rate was inversely dependent on thoria concentration, and on the electrolyte amount as well.

The purpose of the present investigation, using the extinction measurements, was to obtain some insight into the geometry of the flocs formed during the flocculation of ferric vanadate sol with different concentrations of the electrolyte. This study was made with the sol at its different states of purity.

EXPERIMENTAL

A freshly formed precipitate of ferric vanadate was peptized to a clear sol by the addition of 5% FeCl_3 with constant stirring. The positively charged sol thus formed was subjected to dialysis, and various samples were withdrawn at different time intervals. Each sol, withdrawn at a definite time interval, was analysed for Fe_2O_3 , VO_4^{3-} and Cl^- contents in gms/lit, and its purity assessed by observing the precipitation value of K_2SO_4 . Among the various sols thus withdrawn, only three samples of purities 0.13, 0.27, 1.00 (when expressed in terms of ratios of the reciprocal coagulation value of K_2SO_4) were taken and their flocculation studied in terms of the change of extinction of light with the electrolyte concentration. The following procedure was adopted for measuring the extinction values.

A series of the solutions of the electrolyte (K_2SO_4) was arranged in the increasing order of its concentration so that its precipitation value for the sol under investigation was included in the concentration range. Starting with the solution of the least concentration, a volume of 10 ml of each of the series was added to 10 ml of the sol previously arranged in a separate set of pyrex glass tubes, well cleaned by steaming. For each extinction measurement, mixing was done one after the other maintaining the same experimental conditions throughout the course. Use was made of Spekol spectro-colorimeter with the wavelength drum set at 450 nm and the extinction values were observed at different times (1, 3, 5, 7 & 10 mins) of flocculation.

Table I indicates purity of the sol in terms of the reciprocal coagulation values of K_2SO_4 at each stage of its dialysis, and the corresponding Fe_2O_3 , VO_4^{3-} , Cl^- contents in gms/lit.

TABLE I

Composition and purity of ferric vanadate sol at different stages of dialysis

Stages of dialysis	Days of dialysis	Amount in gms/lit of			Coagulation value of K_2SO_4 (millimoles)	Reciprocal coagulation value
		Fe_2O_3 ,	VO_4^{3-} ,	Cl^-		
I	1	7.013	8.530	9.201	2.00	0.5000
II	4	5.641	6.900	6.251	0.98	1.0204
III	7	5.200	6.500	4.006	0.27	3.7037

DISCUSSION

Fig. 1 records the changes that take place in extinction of light with the stepwise addition of the electrolyte amounts to the sol of not much purity. It is seen that the Extinction-concentration curves for all times of flocculation chosen here are comprised of three parts. In the beginning, the changes in extinction are negligible. With the addition of increasing amounts of the electrolyte, the coagulation is accelerated and at a particular

range the extinction of light shoots up. Finally the curves level down and show even a falling trend. The data for purer forms of the sol (vide Table 3 & 4) give similar features if plotted except that the flocs formed in these sols give lower extinction values.

Fig. 1. Extinction concentration curves of ferric vanadate sol I, dialysed for one day. Arrow indicates coagulation value.

Initially, with the addition of lower amounts of the electrolyte, there is still a high potential energy maximum for the interaction of two particles in terms of Verwey's and Overbeek's view describing the interaction of particles according to a repulsive potential arising from the electrical double layer interaction and an attractive potential due to the Van der Waals—London forces. With the increasing amount of the electrolyte, a system is reached in which the attractive potential is greater than the repulsive potential for all separations (an agglomerating suspension). During this process, the primary particles are first connected at random points. It is well established that the process of aggregation itself causes marked change in the distribution of ions between the double layer and the disperse medium. This would bring about a change in the system with just a repulsion left. Under these conditions the particles are expected to get rearranged into the agglomerates of massive and denser structures with firm contacts which turn out to be optically dense. The abrupt rise in extinction values as seen in the Fig. 1 can be attributed to such re-orientation process. When however, still higher concentrations of the electrolyte are taken, the attractive energy

TABLE 2

*Sol I**(Ferric Vanadate Sol dialysed for 1 day)*

<i>M</i> 1, <i>M</i> 35 K_2SO_4 added to 10 ml Sol Total Volume 20 ml.	Extinction Values for				
	1 Minute	3 minutes	5 Minutes	7 Minutes	10 Minutes
0.0	0.060	0.060	0.060	0.060	0.060
1.0	0.070	0.070	0.070	0.070	0.070
2.0	0.090	0.100	0.110	0.130	0.150
3.0	0.140	0.160	0.180	0.210	0.250
4.0	0.240	0.270	0.310	0.350	0.400
5.0	0.400	0.450	0.500	0.550	0.600
6.0	0.580	0.650	0.700	0.790	0.860
7.0	0.760	0.850	1.000	1.100	1.280
8.0	1.040	1.100	1.200	1.290	1.380
9.0	1.080	1.130	1.200	1.250	1.330
10.0	1.050	1.070	1.130	1.150	0.980

TABLE 3

*Sol II**(Ferric Vanadate Sol dialysed for 4 days)*

<i>M</i> 1, <i>M</i> 180 K_2SO_4 added to 10 ml Sol Total Volume 20 ml.	Extinction Values for				
	1 Minute	3 Minutes	5 Minutes	7 Minutes	10 Minutes
0.0	0.050	0.050	0.050	0.050	0.050
1.0	0.060	0.070	0.080	0.080	0.080
2.0	0.080	0.090	0.110	0.130	0.140
3.0	0.120	0.140	0.150	0.170	0.190
4.0	0.170	0.190	0.210	0.230	0.250
5.0	0.230	0.250	0.280	0.310	0.340
6.0	0.360	0.400	0.450	0.500	0.550
7.0	0.530	0.600	0.660	0.720	0.800
8.0	0.800	0.900	0.940	1.010	1.190
9.0	0.950	1.000	1.080	1.150	1.230
10.0	1.000	0.960	1.030	1.070	1.100

TABLE 4

*Sol III**(Ferric Vanadate Sol dialysed for 7 days)*

M1, M/420 K ₂ SO ₄ added to 10 ml Sol Total Volume 20 ml.	Extinction Values for				
	1 Minute	3 Minutes	5 Minutes	7 Minutes	10 Minutes
0.0	0.040	0.040	0.040	0.040	0.040
1.0	0.045	0.045	0.050	0.050	0.060
2.0	0.055	0.060	0.060	0.075	0.080
3.0	0.070	0.080	0.090	0.105	0.120
4.0	0.160	0.175	0.215	0.235	0.270
5.0	0.300	0.330	0.370	0.420	0.450
6.0	0.460	0.480	0.495	0.515	0.540
7.0	0.510	0.520	0.540	0.560	0.580
8.0	0.530	0.545	0.565	0.580	0.595
9.0	0.550	0.565	0.580	0.590	0.600
10.0	0.560	0.540	0.580	0.560	0.470

predominates, and the particles stick where they touch each other. At this stage the aggregates are large in size and so their number per unit volume is small. Consequently the distance between their centres is large, and since the particles are loosely and haphazardly bound together, light can pass through the gaps between the particles and hence absorption of light decreases. Troelstra and Kruyt¹⁰ have described that loosely formed flocs act as feebly scattering Raleigh particles. Taking into consideration 10 minute coagulation curves it is seen that the maximum extinction value that is reached while coagulating a purer sol does not exceed the value $E = 0.600$. This indicates that the extent to which the particles of the flocs rearrange themselves form a denser aggregate is very low as compared to that with impure sols.

A perusal of the curves in Fig. 1 shows that there is a systematic change of the inflection points with the time of flocculation, and consequently better defined coagulation values cannot be obtained from these curves.

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